

Pokkali had significantly higher shoot dry weight and K:Na ratio under saline conditions than IR28 and IR20. In general, the highest salinity level resulted

in much lower shoot dry weights and K:Na ratios. Semitolerant variety IR20 responded best to ABA. □

Effect of salinity and abscisic acid (ABA) application on shoot dry weight and K:Na ratio of 3 rice varieties.

Treatment	Shoot dry weight (mg/plant)				K:Na ratio (shoot)			
	IR28	IR20	Pokkali	Mean	IR28	IR20	Pokkali	Mean
Control ^a	855	912	1095	—	176.1	187.5	125.0	—
Without ABA	409	395	774	526	10.69	8.44	14.21	11.11
With ABA	526	565	764	618	12.39	12.37	14.48	13.08
Mean	468	480	769		11.54	10.41	14.35	
LSD (0.05)								
Variety				81.2				1.10
ABA				66.3				0.90
Variety × ABA				114.8				1.55
Salinity level (dS/m)								
EC10				642				15.27
EC15				502				8.92
LSD (0.05)				66.3				0.90

^aControl values were not included in analysis of variance.

Integrated germplasm improvement – irrigated

MDU4, a high-yielding, cold-tolerant rice for Tamil Nadu

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Screening for cold tolerance in rice in the high area of Cumbum valley in Madurai district of Tamil Nadu, India (nocturnal temperature 12-14 °C Nov-Feb, during the rice crop flowering phase), identified the high-yielding, cold-tolerant line ACM16 (AC2836/Jagannath). It has been named MDU4 and released for planting in cooler regions of Tamil Nadu.

MDU4 is semidwarf, high tillering, and nonlodging. Average yield in adaptive trials was 5.9 t/ha, 17.3% higher than that of IR20 (Table 1). Maximum yield potential is 10.5 t/ha. It matures in 125-130 d.

MDU4 is highly tolerant of low temperature and has lower spikelet sterility than IR20 and MDU2 (Table 2). In addition, it exhibits little grain discoloration, which is a problem in IR20 and

Table 1. Yield of MDU4 (ACM16) in adaptive field trials, Tamil Nadu, India.

Trial site	Yield (t/ha)		
	ACM16 (MDU4)	MDU2	IR20
Madurai district	6.4	6.1	5.7
Dharmapuri	6.4	5.9	5.7
Salem	8.2	7.9	6.4
Overall mean	7.0	6.3	6.1
State seed farms (Keelagudalur Cumbum Valley)	5.4	4.3	4.4
National trials	5.3	—	4.5
Mean	5.9	5.3	5.0

Table 2. Reaction of MDU4 (ACM16) to low temperature.

Variety	Reaction ^a			
	1985-86	1986-87	1987-88	Mean
ACM16(MDU4)	6.6	7.2	9.6	7.8
MDU2	12.4	11.8	14.1	12.7
IR20	16.4	19.5	15.7	13.7

^aBased on % chaffy grain.

MDU2 in low-temperature areas.

MDU4 is resistant to leaf blast, neck infection, sheath rot, and brown leaf spot under field and artificial conditions. It shows moderate resistance to gall midge and brown planthopper. □

Xiangwanxian 2, an excellent grain quality rice variety derived from an IR line

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Xiangwanxian 2, a short-duration, late rice variety derived from IR19274-26-2-3-1-2 (IR2071/IR2153//IR36) introduced from IRRI, was released Mar 1991 in Hunan. Average yield at 15 locations of the regional provincial test was 6 t/ha in 1990. It has 1000-grain weight of 21.2 g, with 83.8% seed fertility.

Grain quality is superior to that of most indica varieties in China: milled head rice is 58.2%, translucent endosperm, length/width ratio 3.9, 16.1% amylose content, 6% chalky grain, 0.7% area with chalkiness, alkali spreading value 3, 9.1% protein content. These characterize Xiangwanxian 2 as a low-amylose, high to intermediate gelatinization-temperature type similar to international market rices. Cooked grains of Xiangwanxian 2 are soft and cohesive.

Xiangwanxian 2 is semidwarf (90-99 cm), erect and nonlodging, heavy tillering, with 110-d duration. It is suitable as a late crop in Hunan. □

HKR228, a semidwarf aromatic rice strain for Haryana, India

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HKR228 (IET10367) is a semidwarf aromatic rice derived from Sona/Basmati 370. In wet season varietal trials 1985-90, HKR228 yielded 50% more than local check Basmati 370 (Table 1).

HKR228 has 143-d duration, 131 grains/panicle, and 1000-grain weight of 19.0 g. Its grain is long and slender with higher hulling and milling recovery than